

Phendata analysis for Chr7 by JW

R Markdown

This is an R Markdown document. Markdown is a simple formatting syntax for authoring HTML, PDF, and MS Word documents. For more details on using R Markdown see <http://rmarkdown.rstudio.com>.

When you click the **Knit** button a document will be generated that includes both content as well as the output of any embedded R code chunks within the document. You can embed an R code chunk like this:

```
##
## >=====
## This version of PhenStat includes *FEWER* functions than the previous ones
## You *still* can use the previous functions by using ':::'. For example :
## PhenStat:::boxplotSexGenotype or PhenStat:::FisherExactTest
## *** Want to know what is new in this version? run PhenStat:::WhatIsNew()
## >=====

## [1] "C:/Users/wottoj/offline/killonedrive/chr7_phenstat"

## Warning:
## Dataset's 'Weight' column is missed.
## You can define 'dataset.colname.weight' argument to specify column for the weight effect modeling.

## Warning:
## Dataset's 'Batch' column is missed.
## You can define 'dataset.colname.batch' argument to specify column for the batch effect modeling.

## Information:
## Dataset's 'Genotype' column has following values: 'C57BL/6J', 'Chr7'

## Information:
## Dataset's 'Sex' column has following value(s): 'Female', 'Male'

## Warning:
## Weight column is not present in the database.

## Information:
## Dependent variable: 'Parameters.Total.Hole.Pokes'.

## Information:
## Perform all MM framework stages: startModel and finalModel.

## Information:
## Method: Mixed Model framework.
```

```

## Information:
## Equation: 'withoutWeight'.

## Information:
## Calculated values for model effects are: keep_Batch=FALSE, keep_EqualVariance=TRUE, keep_Weight=FALSE

##
## Test for dependent variable:
## *** Parameters.Total.Hole.Pokes ***

##
## Method:
## *** Mixed Model framework ***

## -----

## Model Output

## -----

## Final fitted model: Parameters.Total.Hole.Pokes ~ Genotype

## Was batch significant? FALSE

## Was variance equal? TRUE

## Genotype p-value: 8.238139e-01

## Genotype effect: 1.174342e+00 +/- 5.430131e+00

## Was there evidence of sexual dimorphism? no (p-value 9.056407e-01)

## Genotype percentage change Female: 2.74%

## Genotype percentage change Male: 2.74%

##
## -----

## Classification Tag

## -----

## With phenotype threshold value 0.01 - no significant change

##
## -----

## Model Output Summary

```

```
## -----
```

```
##           Value Std.Error   t-value    p-value  
## (Intercept) 42.263158  3.671438 11.5113349 4.260738e-13  
## GenotypeChr7 1.174342  5.430131  0.2162641 8.301132e-01
```

```
““
```

Note that the `echo = FALSE` parameter was added to the code chunk to prevent printing of the R code that generated the plot.